

Effect of Amil Fund from Zakat, Amil Fund from Infaq and Size of Amil to The Performance of Amil Zakat

Achmad Hizazi¹, Fitrini Mansur², Rico Wijaya³

^{1,2,3} Accounting Department, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Jambi

*Corresponding Author: Achmad Hizazi

ABSTRACT: This is the first study to our knowledge analyzes the effect of effect of amil fund from zakat, amil fund from infaq and size of amil to the performance of amil zakat.

Using data from 11 Community based Amil Zakat in national level (LAZ) in 13 years period from 2010 to 2022, we find that amil fund from zakat has effect to positive performance of amil zakat, amil fund from infaq has positive effect to performance of amil zakat and size of amil to has positive effect to the performance of amil zakat. Our novelties Find that Amil fund from zakat and amil fund from infaq has positive effect on performance of amil zakat, and amil fund from zakat has greater effect to performance of amil zakat than the effect of amil fund from infaq to the performance of amil zakat.

KEYWORDS: amil fund from zakat, amil fund from infaq, size of amil and performance of amil zakat.

INTRODUCTION

Attention regarding zakat began to grow after the 1998 reform era, accompanying the growing concern about Islamic economics. Meanwhile, zakat institutions before 1998 had not been formally formed, mostly only in the form of temporary committees in mosques with a greater focus on zakat fitrah. Apart from that, social institutions that manage community aid funds have begun to grow, such as Dompot Duafa in 1994 (www.dompetduafa.org) and other amil zakat infaq and shodaqoh institutions which have begun to grow in various regions. In the New Order era, the existence of Islamic economics was very limited, which was institutionally seen with the emergence of the first Islamic bank with the name Bank Muamalat in 2001 (OJK). Meanwhile, the second sharia bank emerged in 1998 with the support of the legal basis of Law no. 10/1998 concerning Amendments to Law no. 7 1992 concerning banking. In regulating the institution and management of infaq shodaqoh zakat, Law Number 38 of 1999 concerning zakat management emerged. With this legal basis, various other zakat infaq and shodaqoh institutions emerged, such as LAZISMU in 2002 (www.lazismu.org) and other zakat infaq and shodaqoh institutions. In 2011 the government issued Law no. 23 of 2011 concerning zakat management which replaced Law no. 10 of 1998.

The implementation of Law No. 23 of 2011 is strengthened by the existence of government regulation No. 14 of 2014 concerning the implementation of Law No. 23 of 2011 concerning zakat management and Instruction of the President of the Republic of Indonesia No. 03 of 2011 concerning the optimization of zakat collection within the government. Law No. 23 of 2011 confirms that zakat management is managed by two groups of institutions, the Amil Zakat Agency (BAZ) and the Amil Zakat Institution (LAZ). One of the important points in strengthening zakat management is regarding the accountability of zakat management. As an institution that carries out the mandate of the Indonesian Muslim community, accountability is needed to gain the community's trust that BAZ and LAZ are worthy of carrying out this mandate. Nurhasanah and Binamadani (2017) emphasized that to gain the trust of muzakki, zakat amil institutions must report the zakat they manage to the community.

Amil Zakat's accountability can be seen in the financial reports provided or published by Amil Zakat. The financial report contains important points that zakat stakeholders need to know. However, not all stakeholders are able to read well or understand what is presented in financial reports. For example, the amount of zakat collection is presented well in the financial report. Likewise, the distribution of amil or the amil portion of the zakat collected. However, the relationship between the two cannot be read directly in the financial statements. Special research is needed to see this relationship. Muftadi and Susilowati (2018), Risanda et al (2018) and Hizazi et al (2018) have seen that the distribution of amil funds or amil shares has a positive influence on the performance of amil zakat. However, their research has not yet looked at the influence of each part of amil such as the amil part of zakat and the amil part of infaq on the performance of amil zakat. This research will look at the influence of the amil portion of zakat and the amil portion of infaq on the performance of amil jugat. Furthermore, this research will also look at the optimal amil fund rates in improving the performance of amil zakat.

From the background explained previously, it is interesting to carry out research regarding 1) Does Amil Fund from Zakat affect the performance of the Zakat amil? 2) Does Amil Fund from Infaq affect the performance of amil zakat? 3) Does the effect of the Amil Fund from Infaq to the Performance of amil zakat greater than the effect of the Amil Fund from Zakat to the Performance of amil zakat?

This research Novelty looks in detail at the relationship between amil funds and the financial performance of amil zakat. What is the relationship between the amil part of zakat and the financial performance of zakat amil and the relationship between the amil part of infaq and the financial performance of zakat amil. We Find that Amil fund from zakat and amil fund from infaq has positive effect on performance of amil zakat, and amil fund from zakat has greater effect to performance of amil zakat than the effect of amil fund from infaq on performance of amil zakat. Research on the performance of amil zakat was previously conducted by Muhtadi and Susilowati (2018); Hizazi et al. (2022) with OLS regression. And Hizazi et al (2023) looked at the simultaneous relationship between amil funds and amil zakat performance. Meanwhile, Wahab and Rahim (2013) carried out efficiency measurements and Tobit regression was carried out by Al-Parisi (2017).

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Literature Review

a. Islamic corporate governance, Manajer (Amil) and Organizational Performance

It's fascinating to observe how managers affect organizational performance in both the public and private sectors. (Brudney et al., 2001; Nicholson-Crotty and O'Toole, 2004; Buck et al., 2008). Managers have a key role in the direct and indirect management of organizational resources that will enhance organizational performance. Organizational performance will be affected by changes in management. According to Hill (2005), manager turnover initially will have a detrimental effect on performance if managers are hired from outside the firm, but over time, it will have a favorable impact.

Islamic corporate governance isn't supposed to oversee and regulate islamic financial organizations in the same way that it used to. In fact, the intense competition, the failures of the Islamic finance sector that have been noted, the unheard-of difficulties, and the necessary ethical considerations call for a new strategy that will improve organizational performance, ensure its survival in the unhindered competitive environment. It is imperative that Amil Zakat apply islamic corporate governance which are equipped with a comprehensive and innovative effort to enhance its collection and align with best business practices

On the other hand, organizational performance will be impacted by the strategy that managers choose (Boyne and Walker, 2004; Cheon and An, 2016). Even while past strategies do not greatly influence performance, organizations that do poorly are more likely to adopt the posture of defender than prospective. Network impact on performance has been discussed in other studies (Meier and O'Toole 2003). A sample of amil zakat institutions, where management utilize the term amil, is used in this study.

b. Performance of Zakat Institutions

Performance measurement is a critical component to understand For an institution success. Due to the existence of performance indicators that are not held by non-commercial institutions, such as earnings and stock returns (Kaplan 2001), commercial institutions have a very good way of articulating this. This has led to the majority of prior research in zakat institutions adopting the Data Enveloping Analysis approach, which was created by Farel in 1957, to quantify efficiency. While Muhtadi and Susilowati (2018) use regression to test efficiency, another study (Risanda et al., 2018) uses a measure of the production function with stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) based on the Cobb Douglas production function with zakat receipts and distribution as the dependent variable.

The proportion of inputs to outputs generated by zakat institutions is used as the performance variable with efficiency. The following performance metrics have been employed in earlier research: Distribution efficiency has been studied by Muhtadi and Susilowati (2018), Al-Ayubi et al. (2018), Rustyani & Rosyidi (2018), technical efficiency has been studied by Risanda et al. (2018), Al-Ayubi et al. (2018), and productivity measures have been studied by Rustyani & Rosyidi (2018).

The quantity of input and output variables employed demonstrates the range of efficiency metrics applied in earlier studies. The selection of this variable may be based primarily on user desire. However, due to methodological restrictions, Muhtadi and Susilowati (2018) only used 20 observations, and Risanda et al (2018) only used 15 observations, whose results might be biased, Muhtadi and Susilowati (2018) also conducted a regression test with the dependent variables Zakat Collection and efficiency. However, the results were not satisfactory. Hizazi et al. (2022) discovered that amil funds had a favorable impact on performance using the total collection of Zakat, Infaq, and shodawoh as a performance metric.

c. Amil funds and organizational performance

The initial reference for performance research is made to literacy in commercial organizations or companies due to the dearth of research that examines the relationship between amil funds and organizational performance.

According to Jensen and Murphy's (1990) research, executives who get management incentives are more likely to make decisions that are in the best interests of shareholders. In contrast, Tosi et al. (2000) found in a meta-analysis of executive wage research that salary was a variable that was employed in all assessed studies to enhance organizational performance.

Mubtadi & Susilowati (2018) demonstrated in a study of amil zakat that amil funds had a favorable impact on amil zakat. With further samples and observations, Hizazi et al. (2022) support this conclusion that amil finances influence amil zakat performance.

d. Size of Amil Zakat

According to Watt and Zimmermann's political cost theory from 1978, huge corporations are the focus of regulation. Greater material and human resources will be available to the organization as it grows. According to this viewpoint, a company's performance improves with size.

Lee (2009) and Pervan and Visic (20120) demonstrate that business size and performance are positively correlated. This firm size suggests that a company's ability to make more money is correlated with the size of its assets. The ability to manage resources to boost business performance increases with the size of the company.

The size of the corporation can be determined by total asset and how many branches it owns. However, using the quantity of branches to indicate the size of the business is not yet a standard practice. The presence of more branches indicates that the business and the firm are expanding.

e. Previous Research

Performance measures from previous research are Zakat Distribution, Zakat Collection, , Total Assets Zakat Recipient and Zakat Collection efficiency (Ahmad & Main, 2014; Mubtadi & Susilowati, 2018; Al-Ayubi & Possumah, 2018; Rustyani & Rosyidi 2018; Risanda et. al., 2018). These measures are able to explain the extent of the zakat institution's efforts to gather as much zakat as they can.. The quantity of infaq received is an additional option because, unlike zakat, infaq is voluntary rather than reflecting duties that must be met. The more the infaq value, the more the people will trust zakat organizations. While the difference in zakat distribution is greatly influenced by the volume of zakat collected.

Mubtadi and Susilowati (2018) and Hizazi et al. (2022) conducted earlier studies using OLS regression. Al-Parisi (2017) used Tobit regression to measure the efficacy of Wahab and Rahim (2013) before them.

f. Research Framework and Model

According to Rustyani and Rosyidi (2018), the number of expenses incurred and the money Amil Zakat receives will have an impact on how the funds are distributed. While the distribution of funds will be determined by the amount of Zakat collected by UPZ, the amount of operational expenditures and the amount paid by the amil will also have an impact on the amount of Zakat collected. Al-Ayubi et al. (2018) included the quantity of volunteers and the quantity of offices to the list of variables affecting UPZ output in addition to these two. The framework and model of this study are depicted in the image below:

Figure 1.

Research Framework

Amil zakat performance model:

The basic model for measuring LAZ performance (Hizazi et al 2021) is as follows:

$$\text{Performance}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AmilFund} + \beta_2 \text{Size}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Offices}_{it} + e \quad (1)$$

Where :

- Performance = Performance Measure, as measured by the total all Amil Institution Collections.
- β_0 = Constant
- Amil Fund = Distibuted or used of Amil funds measured by amil distribution data
- Size = Amil Institution size, measured by total asset
- offices = Number of Offices , measured by the the number of branch offices, service units and centers
- i = crosssection/institution i
- t = time t
- e = error

The current models of the factors that affect of LAZ performance on amil funds is as follows:

$$\text{Performance}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AmilFZ}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{AmilFI} + \beta_3 \text{Size}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Offices}_{it} + e \quad (2)$$

Where :

- Performance = Performance Measure, as measured by the total all Amil Institution Collections.
- β_0 = Constant
- AmilFZ = CollectedAmil funds From Zakat
- AmilFI = CollectedAmil funds From Infaq
- Size = Amil Institution size, measured by total asset
- offices = Number of Offices , measured by the the number of branch offices, service units and centers
- i = crosssection/institution i
- t = time t
- e = error

2.7. Research Hypothesis

Based on the literature review, previous research as well as the framework and research model above, the hypotheses of this research are as follows:

- H1: Amil Fund from zakat has a positive effect to the Performance of Amil Zakat
- H2: Amil Fund from Infaq has a positive effect the Performance of Amil Zakat
- H3: Amil Fund from Infaq has greater effect than Amil Fund From Zakat on the Performance of Amil Zakat

METHODS

This study uses a quantitative method. Using the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) approach, qualitative methods are utilized in the first stage to investigate the elements that influence the performance of the zakat management unit and decide what factors are thought to have an impact on the performance of the zakat management unit..

The parameters to be investigated using the FGD are chosen as a starting point based on the factors that have been employed in prior studies. The FGD was carried out by modeling the collection and distribution of zakat while highlighting the variables that affect this process. In order to explore as many potential influences on UPZ's performance as feasible, the FGD also featured mindmapping. It concluded with a structured debate on the creation of performance metrics and their influences. The FGD's findings served as the foundation for developing the performance model. All present BAZ and LAZ provided quantitative data based on FGDs, which served as the foundation for the presentation of qualitative descriptive performance measurements. The second testing phase is completed utilizing quantitative testing using multiple regression.

The variables that will be examined in this study are the provision of Total Assets, Number of Amil, Number of Volunteers, Operational Costs and Number of Offices and Total Zakat Collection.

a. Research Data Source

The data used is secondary data in the form of LAZ financial reports available at BAZNAS and each LAZ from 2010 to 2022.

b. Subject/ Research Location

The subjects/locations of the research are BAZNAS and LAZ by looking at the general operational similarities and the same basic management. Focus on Quantitative Testing at the national level LAZ using 12 data from 2010-2022.

c. Research Model

The basic model for measuring LAZ performance is as follows:

$$\text{Performance}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{AmilFund} + \beta_2\text{Size}_{it} + \beta_3\text{Office}_{it} + e \tag{1}$$

We Break amil fund from infaq in the model into specific infaq variable restricted Infaq and unrestricted Infaq.

$$\text{Performance}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{AmilFZ}_{it} + \beta_2\text{AmilFI} + \beta_3\text{Size}_{it} + \beta_4\text{Offices}_{it} + e \tag{2}$$

Where :

- Performance = Performance Measure, as measured by the total all Amil Institution Collections.
- β_0 = Constant
- Amil FZ = Amil Fund form Zakat measured by Distibuted of Amil funds from Zakat
- Amil FI = Amil Fund from Infaq measured by Distibuted of Amil funds from Infaq
- Size = Size ofAmil Zakat, measured by total asset
- Offices = Number of Offices , measured by the the number of branch offices, service units and centers
- i = crossection/institution i
- t = time t
- e = error

d. Operational Variables

Our Variables are measured in following ways :

Performance of Amil Zakat (dependend Variable)	Measured by the total of all Fund Collected. Performance = Zakat Fund + Infaq Fund + Waqf +APBN +
Amil FZ	Amil Fund form Zakat measured by Distibuted of Amil funds from Zakat
Amil FI	Amil Fund form Infaq measured by Distibuted of Amil funds from Infaq
Size	Size ofAmil Zakat, measured by total asset
Offices	Measured by Number of Offices/Branches

e. Analysis Method

Then quantitatively regression testing is carried out using Ordinary least square. The estimations run-in one-time execution using E-views 8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

a. Research Samples

In Indonesia, there are 37 authorized Amil Zakat Institution in National Scale, 33 Amil Zakat Institution in Provincial Level and 70 Amil Zakat in Municipality level according to Indonesia (Religious Ministry, 2023). Our research uses data from Amil Zakat in National Level due to greater fund collected and the complete data availability. Amil Zakat in Provincial and Municipality level has lesser data available in their website.

Table 2. Research Sample

No	Criteria	Sample	obs
1	Authorized National LAZ	37	85
2	Not publish financial report in internet		(27)
3	Incomplete data		(5)
4	Observations	11	73

Effect of Amil Fund from Zakat, Amil Fund from Infaq and Size of Amil to The Performance of Amil Zakat, Vol. 02 Issue 03-2025

From 37 Amil Zakat population in National level we used 11 amil zakat as our samples based on couples criteria, such as availability of the data in internet and completeness of the data , see table 2. There are 85 observations from 12 sample but I sample Yakesma doesn't have complete data required by our models. Finally, only 11 samples selected with 73 observations are available for our model.

b. Statistic descriptive

Our Statistic descriptive listed in thousands of rupiah for our model as follow:

Table 3. Statistic Descriptive

	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Performance	96,896,366	436,000,000	18,653,044	89,238,781
Amil Fund	11,398,506	7,299,911	50,949,016	1,629,805
Amil Fund from Zakat	4,935,678	27,773,029	608,616	6,602,718
Amil Fund from Infaq	8,402,501	28,687,907	1,123,369	7,550,930
Asset	29,461,437	126,000,000	4,293,035	24,710,310

Performance is total fund collected by amil zakat. Amil is Amil Fund Amilz is Amil fund from zakat, amili is amil fund from Infaq and asset is total asset, all variables measured in thousands of rupiah.

Observations: 73

c. Normality and Correlation tests

Normality test for our model using Jarque berra which require its Probability score greater than 0.5. our normality test shows that Jarque Berra score is 1.758890 and probability score is 0.415013 that conclude that our model has normal distribution of data.

Table 4. Correlation

Correlation	Performance	AMIL	Amilz	Amili	Asset
Performance	1 -----				
Amil	0.889253 0.0000	1.000000 -----			
Amilz	0.916772 0	0.769991 0.0000	1 -----		
Amili	0.80218 0	0.640601 0.0000	0.674587 0	1 -----	
Asset	0.423423 0.0002	0.453249 0.0001	0.196132 0.0963	0.477291 0	1 -----

Performance is total fund collected by amil zakat. Amil is Amil Fund Amilz is Amil fund from zakat, amili is amil fund from Infaq and asset is total asset, all variables measured in thousands of rupiah.

Observations: 73

We use correlation tables to check whetr our model has Multi Correlation between its independence variables. Table 4 shows that only Amil Fund (Amil) and Amil Fund From Zakat (amilz) that have correlation greater than 0,7 because Amil Fund from zakat is part from Amil Zakat. But we don't use Amil Fund in our primary model.

d. Results

Following A Risanda et al. (2018) and Hizazi et al. (2021) we check whether Amil Zakat has effect to Performance of Amil Zakat using greater number of observations. Ours result show consistent output that Amil Fund has positive effect to Performance of amil zakat. Thus, in our primary model we use Amil Fund from zakat and and amil Fund from Infaq replacing amil fund to become our independent variables.

Table 4. Results

$$\text{Performanceit} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{AmilFundZakatit} + \beta_2\text{AmilFundInfaq} + \beta_3\text{Sizeit} + \beta_4\text{Officesit}$$

Variable	Coefficient		Coefficient	
C	17.214202 (0)		17.14249 0	
AMILZ	6.45E-08 (0)	***	6.15E-08 0	***
AMILI	3.32E-08 (0)	***	3.25E-08 0	***
Size	9.51E-09 (0)	***	9.06E-09 0	***
Offices	-0.00065 (0.6951)			
Adj R2	0.881034		0.868923	
F-statistic	134.3042		138.0011	
Prob(F-statistic)	0		0	
observations:	73		63	

Lag independent variables

Performance is total fund collected by amil zakat. Amil is Amil Fund Amilz is Amil fund from zakat, amili is amil fund from Infaq and asset is total asset, all variables measured in thousands of rupiah.

Our model uses 2 types of data, in first columns using same periodic data using 73 observations and second column using lag of independent variable which are reduced to 63 observations only.

Performance in this model is financial performance of amil zakat measured by total fund collected by amil zakat that consists of zakat, Infaq, Shodaqah, Waqaf, non halal and others sources of fund. Amilz is amil fund from zakat, allocation of zakat distributed to amil to support its operations. Amili is amil fund from infaq, allocation of infaq distributed to amil to support its operations. Size is size of amil zakat measured by total asset, offices is number office or branches of amil zakat. Office is number of main office and branches owned by amil zakat. Result shows in first column that AMILZ has significant effect on Performance with coefficient score 6.45E-08 with probability score 0 below 0,01 limit confirmed our first hypotheses. AMILI also has significant effect on Performance with coefficient score 3.32E -08 with probability score 0 below 0,01 limit confirmed our second hypotheses. But, coefficient score of AMILZ 6.45E-08 larger than AMILI score 3.32E -08 against our third hypotheses.

We also run our basic model, the result consisten with our result and also support A Hizazi et. All. (2021). This support the roggorous of our second model.

e. Discussion

Effect of amil fund from zakat to the performance of amil zakat

Zakat is main source of fund collected by amil zakat which is compulsory by syariah. However, submitting zakat to amil zakat is voluntary making collecting zakat from muzakki a challenging task. Amil fund from zakat is regulated by BAZNAS at maximum rate 12.5 % of zakat collected. Normally amil zakat take amil zakat near maximum limit.

Result show that coefficient result of amil fund from zakat to performance is 6.45E-08 with probability below 0,01. This result means that amil zakat could optimize amil fund from zakat to support their operation to collect fund from muzakki this is consistent to Risanda et. al., (2018), Hizazi et al (2021), Hizazi et al (2022) that amil fund has positive effect to performance of amil zakat. Amil fund allocated from zakat has no restriction on purpose of fund to spend. Amil zakat may spend on salary of amil or other operational expenses to maximize the collection of funds.

Effect of Amil Fund from Infaq to the performance of amil zakat

Other source of amil fund is Infaq. Infaq has voluntary nature according to syariah which provide other challenge to amil to provide program which may attract donors/muzakki to fund their programs. Some of infaq require amil to follow allocation of fund related to certain programs or follow requisition of donors to certain purpose, however there are infaq that put no restriction to any amil zakat's program. This make infaq come under two categories: restricted infaq and unrestricted infaq.

BAZNAS regulation regarding amil fund from zakat from Infaq limits maximum allocation to 20% of collected infaq, either restricted or unrestricted infaq. It seem that amil may gain more from infaq than from zakat.

Our estimation results show that coefficient of amil fund from infaq is $3.32E-08$ with probability less than 0.01 %. This also means that amil zakat could optimize the amil fund from infaq to fund their operations and other supports to maximize their collection of fund.

However, with the average amount of amil fund from infaq at 8,402,501,000,- which is larger than average amount amil fund from zakat at 4,935,678,000,- we expect that amil fund from infaq could have greater impact than amil fund from zakat. But the results show vice versa this might occur due to some restriction of some of infaq which limit creativity of amil zakat.

Amil fund from zakat has greater effect to performance of amil zakat than the effect of amil fund from infaq on performance of amil zakat. This means that amil zakat put more weight on zakat than infaq to continuously push the performance of amil zakat

Effect of size of amil zakat to the performance of amil zakat

Greater size of amil zakat shows the greater power of amil on size of programs and greater coverage on reaching their donors. Greater amil zakat may cover all province in Indonesia such as rumah zakat and Dompot Duafa, but some amil zakat only cover few provinces like . With greater coverage amil zakat's may interact with more donors which eventually collect more funds.

Our results show that size of amil has coefficient scores at $9.51E-09$ with probability less than 0.01 which mean the bigger amil zakat will have the higher performances of amil zakat. The bigger size of amil zakat provide amil zakat with bigger capabilities to do more in providing more programs and more services. This is consistent with Hizazi et al (2021) that show amil fund has positive effect on performance of amil zakat.

Effect of number of offices to the performance of amil zakat

Number of offices of amil zakat reflects more programs and more coverage of amil zakat. However, our results that number of offices don't have effect on performance of amil zakat. This happened probably due to less variability of number of offices in samples data.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on previous explanations, we conclude that 1) Amil fund from zakat has positive effect on performance of amil zakat. This means amil funds from zakat could push amil zakat to collect more funds from public. 2) Amil fund from Infaq has positive effect on performance of amil zakat. This means that amil fund from infaq also make amil more motivated to provide more service and programs to attract fore funds. 3). amil fund from zakat has greater effect to performance of amil zakat than the effect of amil fund from infaq on performance of amil zakat.

This research implication means that amil zakat could put more weight on collecting fund from zakat than from infaq to push the performance of amil zakat. Fund from zakat provides more continuous availability due to obligative nature of fund.

We recommend to add the contribution of volunteers as a factor that may increase the performance of amil zakat for future researches. Considering wider environment of amil zakat may make future researches have bigger point of views.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, I. H., & Ma'in, M. (2014). The Efficiency of Zakat Collection and Distribution: Evidence from Two Stage Analysis. *Journal of Economic Cooperation & Development*, 35(3).
2. Al-Ayubi, S., & Possumah, B. T. (2018). Examining the Efficiency of Zakat Management: Indonesian Zakat Institutions Experiences. *International Journal of Zakat*, 3(1), 37-55.
3. Al Parisi, S. (2017). Tingkat efisiensi dan produktivitas lembaga zakat di Indonesia. *Esensi: Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 7(1), 63-72.
4. Arieftiara, D., & Utama, S. (2018). Do Financial Reporting Quality and Corporate Governance Have Simultaneous Effect? Evidence from Indonesian Manufacturing Companies. *AKRUAL: Jurnal Akuntansi*, 9(2), 168-185
5. Buck, T., Liu, X., & Skovoroda, R. (2008). Top executive pay and firm performance in China. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 39(5), 833-850.
6. Brudney, J. L., O'Toole Jr, L. J., & Rainey, H. G. (Eds.). (2001). *Advancing public management: New developments in theory, methods, and practice*. Georgetown University Press
7. Cheon, O., & An, S. H. (2017). Blowing in the wind: a study for Granger causality between managerial strategy and organizational performance. *Public Management Review*, 19(5), 686-704
8. Farrell, M. J. (1957). The measurement of productive efficiency. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series A (General)*, 120(3), 253-281.
9. Hill, G. C. (2005). The effects of managerial succession on organizational performance. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 15(4), 585-597

10. Mansour, W., & Bhatti, M. I. (2018). The new paradigm of Islamic corporate governance. *Managerial Finance*, 44(5), 513-523
11. Meier, K. J., & O'Toole Jr, L. J. (2003). Public management and educational performance: The impact of managerial networking. *Public administration review*, 63(6), 689-699
12. Muhtadi, N. A., & Susilowati, D. (2018). Analysis of Governance and Efficiency on Zakat Distribution: Evidence From Indonesia. *International Journal of Zakat*, 3(2), 1-15.
13. Nicholson-Crotty, S., & O'Toole Jr, L. J. (2004). Public management and organizational performance: The case of law enforcement agencies. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 14(1), 1-18
14. Nurhasanah, S., & Binamadani, S. T. A. I. (2018). Akuntabilitas Laporan Keuangan Lembaga Amil Zakat dalam Memaksimalkan Potensi Zakat. *Akuntabilitas*, 11(2), 327-348.
15. Kaplan, R. S. (2001). Strategic performance measurement and management in nonprofit organizations. *Nonprofit management and Leadership*, 11(3), 353-370.
16. Wahab, N. A., & Rahman, A. R. A. (2013). Determinants of efficiency of zakat institutions in Malaysia: A non-parametric approach. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 6(2).
17. Olaniyi, C. O., Obembe, O. B., & Oni, E. O. (2017). Analysis of the nexus between CEO pay and performance of non-financial listed firms in Nigeria. *African Development Review*, 29(3), 429-445
18. Risanda, A., Luthfi, F., & Herianingrum, S. (2018). Measuring the Efficiency of BAZNAS in Managing Zakat Funds with Stochastic Frontier Approach Analysis, 2002–2016. *International Journal of Zakat*, 3(1), 89-107.
19. Rustyani, S., & Rosyidi, S. (2018). Measurement of Efficiency and Productivity of Zakat Institutions in Indonesia using Data Envelopment Analysis and the Malmquist Productivity Index. *International Journal of Zakat*, 3(3), 69-82.
20. Vinayagamoorthi, V., Murugesan, S., Kasilingam, L., & Ramachandran, R. R. (2015). Nexus between Profitability and Environmental Performance of Indian Firms—An Analysis with Granger Causality. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 5(2), 433-439.
21. <https://www.ojk.go.id/id/kanal/syariah/tentang-syariah/Pages/Sejarah-Perbankan-Syariah.aspx>
22. <http://www.dompethuafa.org/about>.